

Acromegaly and Hirsutism: Exploring a Rare Association

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Introduction

Acromegaly is a rare endocrine disorder caused by excessive secretion of Growth Hormone (GH), usually from a pituitary adenoma [1]. Hirsutism, a condition characterized by excessive terminal hair growth in a male pattern in women, has been occasionally reported as a cutaneous manifestation of acromegaly but is rarely the presenting symptom [2, 3]. We report a rare case of acromegaly revealed by hirsutism.

Case Report

A 32-year-old woman was referred by her dermatologist for evaluation of hirsutism associated with oligomenorrhea. Clinical examination revealed acrofacial dysmorphic features consistent with acromegaly, mild hyperandrogenism manifesting as hirsutism with a Ferriman-Gallwey score of 18, and facial acne without signs of virilization.

Laboratory findings included markedly elevated Insulin-like Growth Factor 1 (IGF-1), normal testosterone (0.5 ng/mL), glycated haemoglobin at 6%, normal 8 AM cortisol post-dexamethasone suppression (6 ng/mL), and normal urinary free cortisol and 17-hydroxyprogesterone levels.

Pituitary MRI revealed a macroadenoma, and pelvic ultrasound showed features consistent with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS). Abdominal CT scan was unremarkable. The diagnosis of acromegaly associated with PCOS was established.

Discussion

Acromegaly is a rare disorder, and its link to hirsutism is uncommon but pathophysiologically plausible. GH hypersecretion induces insulin resistance and compensatory hyperinsulinemia, which may stimulate ovarian androgen production and contribute to PCOS and hirsutism [4, 5]. While PCOS is a common cause of hirsutism, its association with acromegaly requires careful endocrine evaluation to guide management.

Conclusion

This case highlights the rare presentation of acromegaly revealed by hirsutism, underscoring the importance of considering GH excess in patients with atypical hyperandrogenic symptoms. Early diagnosis may improve outcomes through targeted therapy.

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